

Spectrophotometric Studies of Titanium(IV) Complexes with *o*-Dihydroxycoumarins. Part I

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*Spectrophotometric studies of titanium(IV) complexes with esculetin and its 4-methyl derivative have been carried out and the possible use of these reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of titanium has been suggested.

The use of *o*-dihydroxycoumarins for the gravimetric determination of titanium has already been reported¹. Esculetin and its derivatives have now been found to form orange-red, water-soluble complexes with titanium. The present investigations relate to the spectrophotometric studies of titanium complexes with esculetin and 4-methylesculetin and the possible use of these reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of this metal. Complexes of titanium with the above reagents at pH 2.0-8.0 show maximum absorption between 385 m μ and 420 m μ . Detailed observations have, however, been carried out at pH 5.5, as above this pH, the reagents have significant optical densities. The complexes obey Beer-Lambert's law at 420 m μ and 400 m μ in the concentration range of 3.0-5.0, p.p.m. of titanium respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Esculetin and 4-methylesculetin were prepared by the usual methods² and their 10⁻³M ethanolic solutions were employed. Titanium solution, prepared by dissolving titanium hydroxide in HCl (conc.) was standardised with oxine. Sodium perchlorate used was of L. R., B.D.H. quality.

Unicam spectrophotometer SP 600 was used for absorption studies. Beckman pH-meter, model H2, with suitable glass electrode was employed for the measurement of pH, which was adjusted with solutions of acetic acid and ammonium acetate.

Absorption Spectra of Titanium Complexes.—The wave length at which the titanium complexes with esculetin and 4-methylesculetin showed maximum absorption increased with increase in pH between 2.0 and 8.0 (Figs. 1 and 2). Absorption studies in each case were, however, carried out only at 420 m μ and 400 m μ respectively at pH 5.5, as above this pH, the reagents showed significant absorption.

Minimum Amount of the Reagent required for Full Colour Development.—The minimum amount of the reagent required for full colour development was six times in the case

1. Jain and Singh, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 317.

2. Amiard and Allais, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1947, 512.

of titanium-esculetin and four times in the case of titanium-4-methylesculetin complex. As excess of the reagent did not cause any interference, the concentration of the reagent in each case was maintained at ten times that of the metal ion.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of titanium-esculetin complex.

FIG. 2. Absorption spectra of titanium-4-methylesculetin complex.

Molar Composition and Stability of Titanium (IV) Complexes.—Molar composition of titanium(IV) complexes with esculetin and 4-methylesculetin in 20% ethanolic solutions, as determined by Job's method³ of continued variations, was found to be 1:3 (Figs. 3 and 4).

FIG. 3. Molar composition of titanium-esculetin complex by Job's method.

FIG. 4. Molar composition of titanium-4-methylesculetin complex by Job's method.

The optical densities of these complexes remained unchanged for 24 hours and these obeyed Beer-Lambert's law at 420 m μ and 400 m μ in the concentration range upto 3.0 p.p.m. and 5.0 p.p.m. of titanium, respectively.

Stability Constants of Titanium(IV) Complexes.—Stability constants of titanium(IV) complexes with esculetin and 4-methylesculetin were determined spectrophotometrically. Two solutions having different ratios of titanium(IV) and the reagent, but at constant ionic strength (0.4M) and containing 20% ethanol, were prepared such that their optical densities were either equal or nearly so. As the molar composition of the complexes was 1:3 and the dissociation constant of the given pair of reactants assuming constant, the value of k was calculated from the relation:

$$k = \frac{(Mke_3)}{[(C_{M_1} - Mke_3)] [(C_{ke_1} - 3(Mke_3))]^3} = \frac{(Mke_3)}{[(C_{M_2} - Mke_3)] [C_{ke_2} - 3(Mke_3)]^3}$$

where C_{M_1} and C_{M_2} are initial concentrations of titanium(IV), C_{ke_1} and C_{ke_2} are the initial concentrations of the ligand, and (Mke_3) denotes the concentration of the complex formed. The mean values of $\log k$ from several determinations at 20° and in 20% ethanolic solutions were found to be (i) Ti—esculetin complex = 8.8 and (ii) Ti—4-methylesculetin complex = 10.7

Interference due to Foreign Ions.—Due to great tendency of *o*-dihydroxy compounds to form metal complexes, the following cations: beryllium, nickel, thorium, tungsten, uranium, cerium (III & IV), copper, iron (II & III), molybdenum, and zirconium have been found to cause interference. Limits of interference due to common anions for 0.5 p.p.m. of titanium are shown below.

TABLE I

Concentration of foreign ions that do not cause interference.

Anion.	Concentration limit with	
	Ti—esculetin complex.	Ti—4-methylesculetin complex.
Borate	30 p.p.m.	150 p.p.m.
Citrate	10	20
Fluoride	20	50
Oxalate	20	150
Phosphate	20	200
Sulphate	20	200

Recommended Procedure for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Ti(IV).—An aliquot amount of the solution containing not more than 3.0 p.p.m. of titanium in the case of esculetin and 5.0 p.p.m. of titanium in the case of 4-methylesculetin was mixed with ten times the amount of the respective reagents. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 5.5 with acetic acid and ammonium acetate buffer and its optical density measured against the reagent under identical conditions. Concentration of titanium could be found from a calibration curve obtained with solutions of known strength. The ions that cause interference should be absent during the estimation.

Dissociation constants (pK) of esculetin (7.6) and 4-methylesculetin (7.9) have been reported earlier⁴. It has now been found that 4-methylesculetin forms a more stable complex than esculetin. In the case of molybdenum also more stable complexes⁴ were formed with more basic reagents. This appears to show that the factors influencing the bonding of hydrogen in the reagents have similar effects on the bonding of the metal in the complexes.

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